

**THE UNIQUENESS OF FILMING TECHNOLOGY IN INDIAN AND
UZBEK FILMS**

Husan Alijanov

State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan

"Sound directing and cinematography skills"

teacher of the department

Annotation: The topic is all information related to the artistic features of filming technology in Uzbek and Bollywood films, new technological principles, their practical achievements and disadvantages. In addition, it aims to analyze the creative cooperation between the two countries in artistic and scientific terms. In this regard, it is necessary to study the principles of operation of modern technical and technological means, new cameras, new formats of lighting technology and their practical application.

Keywords: cinematography, art, history, Object, Camera, color, light, composition, Symmetry, cinema, School of cinematography, creativity, art, graphic solution.

**HINDISTON VA O‘ZBEKISTON FILMLARIDA TASVIRGA OLISH
TEKNOLOGIYASINING O‘ZIGA XOSLIGI**

Husan Alijanov

O‘zbekiston davlat san’at va madaniyat instituti

"Ovozli rejissyorlik va operatorlik mahorati"

kafedrasi o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: O‘zbek va Bollivud filmlarida suratga olish texnologiyasining badiiy xususiyatlari bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan barcha ma‘lumotlar, yangi texnologik tamoyillar, ularni amaldagi yutuq va kamchiliklari xususida. Qolaversa, ikki davlatlar o‘rtasidagi ijodiy hamkorliklarni badiiy va ilmiy tarizda tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Bu borada hozirgi kundagi texnik-texnologik vositalar, yangi kameralarni yangi formatlar yoritish texnologiyalarini o‘zlashtirish va amalda qo‘llash prinsiplarini o‘rganishdan iborat.

Kalit so‘zlar: operator, san‘at, tarix, o‘bektiv, fotokamera, rang, yorug‘lik, kompozitsiya, simmetriya, kino, kinooperatorlik maktabi, ijodkor, badiiylik, tasviriy yechim.

УНИКАЛЬНОСТЬ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ СЪЕМОК В ИНДИЙСКИХ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ФИЛЬМАХ

Хусан Алиджанов

Государственный институт искусства и культуры Узбекистана

«Звукорежиссерское и операторского мастерство»

преподаватель кафедры

Аннотация: емой является вся информация, связанная с художественными особенностями технологии съемок в узбекских и болливудских фильмах, новыми технологическими принципами, их практическими достижениями и недостатками. Кроме того, он направлен на анализ творческого сотрудничества между двумя странами в художественном и научном плане. В связи с этим необходимо изучать принципы работы современных технических и технологических средств, новых камер, новых форматов светотехники и их практического применения.

Ключевые слова: оператор, искусство, история, объектив, фотоаппарат, цвет, свет, композиция, симметрия, кино, школа кинооператоров, креатив, искусство, графическое решение.

The uniqueness of filming technology in Indian and Uzbek films

The 21st century is the age of technology. This "prophecy", which was widely spoken during the transition to the 21st century, finds its confirmation today, whether it is in industry or in the field of art. Although cinema is the "oldest" art form, it is the most scientifically and theoretically studied field as an object of research. Because this type of art differs from other types of art by its wide audience, ideological-artistic scope and universality. The formation of cinema as a synthetic art led to the diversity of theorists' views. In particular, when studying films as technical technologists, their views differ from each other in their ideological direction, approach to film art from different angles, and set different demands on film art.

Although the theoretical study of cinematography has been started early, there is still a great need to study it from a technical technological point of view. One or another aspect of cinema has been studied in the scientific research of scientists working in this field.

The human mind is capable of making unprecedented discoveries. This series of creativity has been continuously developing since the beginning of the world until today. According to this criterion, the limit of millennia separated the human being from materiality and raised it towards spirituality. Already, at the root of this word is "... an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, to grow up in his heart, strengthens his inner world, his will, completes his faith, and awakens his conscience." During this period of striving for the highest, man felt the need to understand existence, to express the vision of inner experiences, to react to the events happening around him, and these processes came to light through the medium of art. However, this field, which is engaged in difficult and noble work, is in sync with life and is always in communication with the life of society.

When talking about technological tools in the art of cinema, it directly goes back to the French brothers Leumers. A lot of scientific research was done before the motion picture camera was created and the first picture was taken, and in 1895 the Lumer brothers put the first motion picture on film and presented it to the public at the Cafe Grant in France. After that, the art of cinema began to develop, and in its place, demands and changes were made to film technology.

Today, the demand for film art is increasing. Cinema, like any visual art, should be considered as an expression of attitude towards life. Technical technological means serve only as a means to achieve the goal. The technological methods of film shooting are different in each country, because ideological ideas, mentality, world view, national idea concepts are different in different countries, therefore, the artistic concepts of film shooting technologies are also different. Movies should be able to put forward a certain idea and convince the viewer of the event and provide spiritual nourishment.

Images created in films, artistic depiction of life, aesthetic perception of events, make a great contribution to the practice of influencing imagination and worldview. Today is not called the age of technology for nothing. Because the opportunities for cinematographers are very large, and the opportunities to get angles and frames from any desired angle have been created. It is worth noting that in the early days of cinema, cameras were several hundred times larger than today's technology, lenses were not interchangeable, and actors and actresses acted closer and further away from the camera, which means that the camera did not move or even move. Today, even filming with the help of a drone and various electronic rails, even making actors in the graphics and screening them, gives the opportunity to create animations of various animals

Therefore, it is said that the technical technological base is an integral part of the cinematographer and serves as a tool for expressing his artistic approach and applying it to the public.

Today, the world's cinematography technology has grown to such a rapid level of development that the technologies are being updated every day, which in turn leads

to the development of the art of cinema, the development of complex images and the expansion of possibilities. When it comes to filming technology, it is necessary to regularly study and practice the technical features of camera lights and optics, which are integral to this cinematographer.

A hotly debated topic today is the transition from film to digital imaging and their technological challenges are still debatable. For example, when it comes to Bollywood film shooting technologies, the techniques of Uzbek film operators are completely different. In India today, film shooting has been completely switched to digital imaging and this opportunity is being used effectively, a clear example of this is the variety of angles of shots. Today, Uzbek cinematographers successfully use RED DRAGON, SONY ALFA, CANON cameras. Indian cinematographers are using Arri alexa sxt, Arri mini, Sony f55 cine alta cameras. Most of the world's cinematographers shoot in arri raw 2.8 format and this is developing day by day. This format ensures high quality in the post production process. The light color sensitivity matrices of the mask camera allow you to take pictures easily using natural light without low lights. This increases the credibility of film images, the camera's capabilities are considered high due to the very high color gamut. Special attention is paid to Bollywood lights and lighting technology. Dino, Mool beam, Arri, kino flo, soft box and various technologies are especially important here. Skilled cinematographers masterfully use the capabilities of these technical devices. Indian cinematographers have mastered the art of lighting. Their images are completely different from other cinematographers. Bright colors, different lighting effects and camera movements are important in the images. The practice of using the crane and rails together is remarkable and provides great convenience to the operator. In this case, the crane is moved together with the rail, as a result of which it is possible to shoot from the crane to even a large plan without interrupting the shot.

Uzbek cinematographers are also applying technical and technological features and strengthening their new technical base. New technologies are being introduced and

widely implemented. One of these is Arri mini, Arri classic cameras. The possibilities of hidden cameras are extremely large and are widely used in world cinematography. These cameras have been used in the Bollywood film industry for many years. Uzbek filmmakers have started shooting in 2.8k Raw format. Maskur format increases the image quality in Uzbek cinematography and makes it easier to give artistic polish. This format also gives a great opportunity to correct errors and flaws accidentally made during the recording process.

In Indian cinema, special attention is paid to aesthetic beauty. Films fascinate the viewer due to the depiction of beautiful nature, beautiful boys and girls, in short, the beauty of existence. Especially the beauty of Bollywood actresses does not leave the viewer indifferent. In fact, the display of this beauty shows the mastery of the photography technique. It is clear from these images that the cinematographer has mastered the technical and technological aspects. This is made possible by placing the lights correctly and according to the shape of the actress's face, making the power of the light very soft and soft, as well as using lens filters as assistants. Currently, cinematographers often use classic soft, warm soft, and black frost filters. This ensures that the portrait will turn out to be extremely beautiful on a large scale. Lighting styles also depend on the importance of the image.

That is why the main characters stand out from the secondary characters, especially episodic and mass characters. Such imaging technologies are changing and developing very rapidly. This requires the cinematographer to constantly work on himself, to improve his skills and, most importantly, to study new technological tools, changes and innovations.

In short, technological tools have become an integral part of the Cinematographer today. Today, technological changes are raising the work of cinematography to a higher level, it should be mentioned that the transition from film to digital cinematography is a clear example of this, and instead it has expanded the technical and technological possibilities of the work of cinematography. Foreign filmmakers are reaching the level

of creating new technologies for films, depending on the genre, which is the reason for the development of film art and technology.

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